

**A STUDY ON TYPE OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS LEARNING
MATHEMATICS AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH ACADEMIC
ACHIEVEMENT AMONG NINTH STANDARD STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Learning mathematics does not only involve thinking and reasoning, it is dependent on the attitudes of the learners towards learning and mathematics. The affective component of attitude is the feeling or emotions of the individual associated with learning mathematics. Thus, the affective component is the source of driving the engagement of students towards mathematics. Furthermore, the affective aspect is also influenced by the belief formed from the cognitive component of attitude, which creates a mindset that becomes constant over time and influences the feelings of the students towards learning mathematics. Students feeling confident in doing mathematics is linked with being successful in mathematics, which is regarded as a positive behaviour.

The present study intended to study the type attitude towards learning mathematics and relationship between academic achievement and attitude among ninth standard students. The sample of the study was 100 ninth standard students from two schools. A standardized tool namely Sodhi's Attitude Scale was administered and collected data was analysed by statistical techniques namely mean, SD, 't' test and Karl Pearson's product moment correlation. The major findings of the study: 14% of the students showed positive attitude towards learning mathematics, 59% of the students showed neutral attitude and 27% of the students showed negative attitude towards learning mathematics. There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of boys and girls of ninth standard students. Study also revealed that there is a strong relationship between attitude towards learning mathematics and academic achievement of ninth standard students. Implications of the study suggested in detail in the study.

Keywords: Attitude towards learning mathematics, academic achievement, mathematics.

1.0.0 Introduction

Attitude towards mathematics plays a crucial role in the teaching and learning processes of mathematics. It affects students' achievement in mathematics. The teaching method, the support of the structure of the school, the family and students' attitude towards school affect the attitudes towards mathematics. Usually, the way that mathematics is represented in the class room and perceived by students, even when teachers believe they are presenting it in an authentic and context dependent way tends to alienate many students from mathematics (Barton, 2000; Furinghetti and Pekkonen, 2002). Researchers concluded that positive attitude towards mathematics leads students towards success in mathematics.

1.1.0 Need for the study

It was found that the various factors hindering students' learning of mathematics constituted student characteristics, teacher characteristics and class/school administration factors which are consistent with the academic achievement. Students' characteristics involve the lack of seriousness, fear of mathematics, fear of the teacher being angry, and fear of failing. The paper sought to investigate students' attitudes towards learning mathematics. It specifically sought to find the relationship between attitudes towards learning mathematics with academic achievement.

1.2.0 Statement of the Problem

A study on type of attitude towards learning mathematics and its relationship with academic achievement among ninth standard students in Kozhikode city in Kerala in relation to their Gender.

1.3.0 Operational definitions of the key terms

Attitude

Attitudes are general evaluations that people hold regarding a particular entity, such as an object, an issue, or a person or a subject. An individual may hold a favourable or positive attitude toward a particular subject, and an unfavourable or negative attitude toward another subject. These attitudes reflect the individual's overall summary evaluations of each subject.

In the present study attitude towards learning mathematics was assessed by standardized tool.

Academic Achievement:

Academic achievement is the capability to achieve academically. It is reflected by the percentage of marks obtained in Class 8th and 9th examination conducted by Kerala state board.

High Achievers: High achievers are those whose scores academic performance is above average.

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Low Achievers: Low achievers are those whose scores academic performance is below average.

1.4.0 Objectives of the study

1. To study the status of student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.
2. To study the student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of gender.
3. To study the status of academic achievement of ninth standard students
4. To study the academic achievement of ninth standard students based on gender.
5. To study the relationship between academic achievement and attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

1.5.0 Hypotheses of the study

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the attitudes of boys and girls of 9th standard students towards learning mathematics.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between the academic achievement of boys and girls of 9th standard students.

Ho3: There is no relationship between attitude towards learning mathematics and academic achievement of 9th standard students.

1.6.0 Methodology

The present study was a descriptive survey on attitude towards learning mathematics and academic achievement among ninth standard Boys and Girls. The research was conducted in Five phases and it is given in table 1.6.1

Table 1.6.1 Research Design

Phase 1	Selection of the variables involved in the study
Phase 2	Study of the related literature
Phase 3	Selection of the standardised tool to measure the carriable attitude towards learning mathematics
Phase 4	Collection of Data
Phase 5	Analysis and interpretation of data

1.7.0 Variables of the study

Two variables were selected. i.e

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- i) Attitude towards learning mathematics
- ii) Achievement

1.8.0 Tools used in the study

Sodhi’s Attitude Scale constructed and standardized by Dr. Sodhi.was used

1.9.0 Population of the study

All the standard nine students who are studying in Kozhikode city in Kerala who study state syllabus

1.9.1 Sample of the study

The sample of the study included 100 students of class 9th .

- b. Area: Urban
- c. Number of schools: two
- d. Number of students: 100
- e. Gender: Girls and Boys
- f. Strata: 2 (Girls and Boys)
- g. Type of schools: Government aided.
- h. Medium: Malayalam

1.10.0 Procedure for data collection

To conduct the study the investigator selected Sodhi’s Attitude Scale (SAS) constructed by Dr. Sodhi. The test comprises of subsets viz.. Attitude towards teachers and parents, Attitude towards discipline, Attitude towards life and humanity, Attitude towards country and Attitude towards religion. With these subsets the Investigator developed an attitude test towards Mathematics. The draft of the test containing 100 items was prepared covering six different sub-tests. Necessary instructions and directions were worked for the entire six sub-tests. A separate response sheet and scoring key were also prepared. Following this, the test was carried out on a sample of 100 students of class 9th of St. Michael’s Girls, HSS, West hill and St. Joseph’s Boys HSS in Kozhikode District. The test was done in order to

- (i) Obtain objective information of each and every item
- (ii) Arrange the selected items in ascending order of difficulty and

(iii) Fix up the time limit for each sub-test.

The pupils were given enough time to complete the test. They were clearly instructed how to attempt the items for all the five subtests.

1.11.0 Statistical techniques used in the study

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyse and interpret the data. In the present study the statistical techniques such as Mean, standard deviation, ‘t’ test and Karl Pearsons product moment correlation ‘r’ value was calculated.

1.12.0 Analysis of the objectives

The presentation of the results and their interpretation has been done objective wise.

1.12.1 Analysis of objective One

The first objective of the study the status of student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard Nine

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores on student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

Table1.1: showing the frequencies of the scores on student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th.

Level	Number of students	Percentage
Positive	14	14%
Neutral	59	59%
Negative	27	27%

As per the tool Range of attitude level was mentioned below

Positive: 64 – 100; Neutral: 57 – 63; Negative : below 57

From the above table 1.1, it is concluded that only 14% of students showed positive attitude towards learning mathematics, 59% students have neutral attitude towards learning mathematic and 27 % students showed negative attitude towards learning mathematics.

Thus, it is concluded that majority of ninth standard students exhibited average level of attitude

towards learning mathematics.

1.12.2 Analysis of objective Two

The second objective of the study was to find out the student's attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of Gender. In order to check the significance of this difference null hypothesis was formulated as;

H_0 : There is no significant difference in attitude towards learning mathematics of ninth standard boys and girls

The analysis and interpretation of the data related to this hypothesis was done with Mean, standard deviation, and 't' test. The result has been presented in table 1.2

Table 1.2: Summary of N, Mean, SD, t-value of the scores of attitude towards learning mathematics of standard nine in terms of Gender.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	't' value	Result
Boys	50	40.12	9.18	1.276	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	40.71	10.45		

From the above table 1.2, it reveals that calculated 't' value is less than the table value. Therefore, null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference between the attitudes of boys and girls of 9th standard students towards learning mathematics.

Thus, it is concluded that both boys and girls do not differ in their attitude towards learning mathematics.

1.12.3 Analysis of objective three

The third objective of the study was to find out the status of academic achievement of ninth standard students.

The following table shows the frequencies of the scores of academic achievements of ninth standard students.

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Table1.3: showing the frequencies of the scores of academic achievements of ninth standard students.

Level	No. of students	Percentage
High	12	12%
Average	58	58%
Low	30	30%

From the above table 1.3, it is concluded that only 12% of students exhibit high level in academic achievement, 58% of students are average on academic achievement level and 30 % are low on academic achievement level.

Thus, it is concluded that majority of ninth standard students fall under average level in achievement in mathematics.

1.12.4 Analysis of objective four

The fourth objective of the study was to find out the status of academic achievement of ninth standard students based on gender. In order to check the significance of this difference null hypothesis was formulated as;

H_0 2: There is no significant difference in academic achievement of secondary school Boys and Girls

The analysis and interpretation of the data related to this hypothesis was done with Mean, standard deviation, and ‘t’ test. The result has been presented in table 1.4

Table 1.4: Summary of N, Mean, SD, t-value of the scores of academic achievement of secondary school Boys and Girls.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	‘t’ value	Remark
Boys	50	36.78	9.4	1.09	Not significant at 0.05 level
Girls	50	37.33	8.9		

From the table 1.4, it is clear that the calculated ‘t’ value is less than the table value. Therefore, null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference between the academic achievement of boys and girls of 9th standard students’ is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. Research hypothesis was rejected. Thus, it is concluded that both Boys and Girls do not differ in their achievement in mathematics.

1.12.5 Analysis of objective five

The fifth objective of the study was to find out the relationship between academic achievement and attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

In order to check the significance of this difference null hypothesis was formulated as;

H₀3: There is no significant relationship between academic achievement and attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

The analysis and interpretation of the data related to this hypothesis was done with Mean, standard deviation, and ‘r’ value. The result has been presented in table 1.5

Table 1.5: Summary of N, Mean, SD, ‘r’ value of the scores of academic achievement and attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	‘r’ value	Remarks
Attitudes towards learning Mathematics	100	39.61	5.9	2.298	Significant at 0.05 level
Achievement in Mathematics	100	40.31	7.11		

From the above table 1.5, it is clear that the calculated ‘t’ value (2.298) is greater than the table value (1.96) significance at 0.05 level. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the research hypothesis is accepted.

Thus, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between academic achievement and attitude towards learning mathematics of 9th standard students.

1.13.0 Major findings of the study

1. The majority of students fall under Neutral level of attitude, it means that status of student’s attitude towards learning mathematics of standard 9th is neutral.
2. Both Boys and Girls do not differ in their attitude towards learning mathematics.
3. The status of academic achievement of ninth standard students is average.
4. Both Boys and Girls do not differ in their achievement in mathematics.
5. There is a significant relationship between attitude towards learning mathematics and academic achievement of 9th standard students.

1.14.0 Educational implications and recommendations of the study

Attitude towards Mathematics

In the present study, the attitude towards mathematics of 9th class students was studied by the investigator. Based on the study, the following recommendations were given to develop more favourable attitude towards mathematics.

1. Educational institutions should organize mathematical seminars, competitions, mathematical fairs in order to capture the interest of the students and ultimately leads to positive attitude towards mathematics.
2. There should be provision of mathematical association and mathematical clubs and students should be encouraged to actively participate in the activities of these clubs and associations.
3. While framing curriculum and educational policies, attitude and interest of the students must be taken into consideration in order to have the strong mathematical ability. Subject mathematics should be correlated with some recreational games and play way methods.
4. For effective instruction and learning in mathematics, clarity of the concept is very important for a teacher. The explanation of the teacher of each and every topic creates more and more curiosity, interest and positive attitude towards mathematics.
5. In order to inculcate the positive attitude among students, mathematics teacher should spend enough time for improving the basic mathematics skills using various shortcut methods, mathematical games and puzzles.

1.15.0 Suggestions for further research

The following are the suggestions for research in the future:

- ❖ The present study was conducted with a sample of 100 students. The same study can be conducted with large samples.
- ❖ The present study was restricted to only 9th standard students. It can be extended to other classes also.
- ❖ The present study was conducted in Kozhikode district in Kerala state. The study can be replicated on other districts of Kerala state.
- ❖ The present study can also be conducted at other levels of school education also.
- ❖ A comparative study can be done to know the difference between government and private school students, general and reserved category students.

1.16.0 Limitations of the study

- The sample was limited. The same study can be conducted with large number of samples.
- The present study was restricted to students of 9th standard in Kozhikode city.
- The study was restricted to two government aided schools of Kozhikode city.
- The study was restricted to the variables i.e. attitude and academic achievement.
- The study was conducted in very small area.

Conclusion

The present study aimed at analyzing the relationship between attitude and academic achievement in mathematics of class 9th students, with special variables like attitude and academic achievement. The study indicates that there is significant differences and relationship between the variables.

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